

The Anxiolytic Effects of an Acute Bout of Resistance Exercise in Young Women

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Generalized anxiety disorder is a common debilitating chronic condition, with women twice as likely to experience in their lifetime. Frontline treatments such as SSRIs (Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors) and CBT (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) are often costly, inaccessible, with some reporting negative side effects. Resistance exercise is emerging as a potentially beneficial, low-cost, easily accessible treatment option. Resistance exercise training has a myriad of physical health benefits but less is known about its acute psychological impact. This study examined the effects of moderate-to-high intensity resistance exercise compared to low-intensity on state anxiety in young women with analogue generalized anxiety disorder.

Research Findings

Both moderate-to-high and low-intensity resistance exercise produced significant reductions in state anxiety and feelings of tension in young women with analogue generalised anxiety disorder, with no meaningful difference between intensities. Notably, even the low-intensity sham condition (just 20% of est 1RM – one repetition maximum) yielded large anxiolytic effects, suggesting the benefits may begin at very light loads. Crucially, these psychological improvements were independent of participants' expectations, suggesting that the effects were driven by the exercise itself rather than any placebo influence.

Policy Implications

Resistance exercise should be formally integrated into acute anxiety management guidelines for young women, with explicit acknowledgement that low-intensity is as effective as moderate-to-high intensity for beginners. Current physical activity recommendations focused on aerobic exercise should be broadened to include more specific resistance-exercise recommendations. Healthcare practitioners and mental health professionals should consider resistance exercise as a low-barrier, accessible intervention for acute anxiety management. Community fitness facilities and student health services should offer entry-level resistance exercise programmes specifically targeting anxious populations.

Industry Recommendations

Exercise practitioners for mental health should be considered as part of multi-disciplinary care teams in the treatment of anxiety disorders. Fitness industry professionals, including personal trainers and gym instructors, should design beginner-friendly resistance exercise programmes using light loads, removing the intimidation barrier that often deters anxious individuals from engaging.

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Further Reading:

Rice, J.M., O'Sullivan, D., Gordon, B.R., Lindheimer, J.B., Monroe, D.C., Lyons, M & Herring, M.P. (2026) Acute effects of moderate-to-high intensity resistance exercise compared to a low-intensity sham attention-control on anxiety related outcomes in young women: A randomized controlled trial, *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 30, 100781. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2026.100781>

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